

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: this article discusses the importance of computer technology in education. Ways to further increase the efficiency of the educational process and form it based on computer technologies are shown.

Key words: computer, advantages of computer learning, creative skills, computer technology.

In a dynamically changing world, the complexity and constant improvement of technology, information in the field of education is of great importance. The current stage of society's development poses a number of fundamental new problems to the educational system, among which is the need to increase the quality of education and its convenience, create optimal educational systems, and strengthen the connection between different levels of education. highlighted. One of the effective ways to solve these problems is the use of computer technology.

The emergence of computer technologies made it possible to create a qualitatively new educational environment as a basis for the development and modernization of the educational system. Computer technology is important at all stages of the education system.

At every stage of cognitive activity, computer technologies perform the functions of both knowledge tools and knowledge objects in all fields of scientific research and knowledge. Thus, innovations in computer technology provide a

revolutionary development of the educational process. Computer technologies belong to the class of innovative technologies, they ensure the rapid accumulation of intellectual potential, guaranteeing the sustainable development of society. The effectiveness of using computer technologies, especially picture textbooks, and the realization of their didactic potential in the educational process is undoubtedly the most important requirement. The use of visualization forms that not only supplement verbal information, but also act as information carriers should help to increase the mental activity of students [1]. Tables, graphs, charts, audiovisual aids, etc. are components of printed and electronic educational materials and play an important role in the development of intellectual and cognitive activity of students [2].

The appropriateness of using computer technologies in the educational process is determined by the effective implementation of didactic principles such as presence, visibility, awareness and activity with their help.

Computer technologies provide the following opportunities for the educational process:

- rational organization of cognitive activities in the educational process;
- involving different categories of students according to their abilities and learning style in the active learning process;
- making the educational process more effective by covering all types of students' emotional perception;
- acquisition and strengthening of professional skills;
- increase the level of self-education, motivation for educational activities;
- to give the student a large amount of knowledge;
- development of intellectual and creative abilities;
- work with various information sources;
- introduction of world trends in education;

- to have access to a single global information space.

Thanks to the use of computer technologies, it will be possible to build an open educational system. The methods and technologies of formation of educational content are being improved. The educational system is becoming more flexible due to the automation of many routine processes, and its response to changes in the surrounding world is accelerating. Modern methods of organizing educational material increase the efficiency of its use, and the introduction of computer technologies allows choosing the optimal set of technologies for organizing the educational process, increasing the efficiency and adequacy of educational system management mechanisms.

Computer technology opens up the opportunity for teachers to abandon the usual educational activities characteristic of traditional teaching, gives him the opportunity to use forms of intellectual work, frees him from presenting an important part of the educational material. The use of new technologies allows the student not only to learn the subject better, but also to master the acquired skills.

Within the framework of the use of computer technologies in the educational process, there are two directions - personalization of the educational process and its technology.

Personalization includes feedback using communication techniques between the student and the teacher. The second is a significant expansion of the student audience. If in the context of personalization of education, the student is an active participant in the exchange of information, when included in large-scale e-learning projects, his role is limited to the consumption and assimilation of information. Both of these approaches are present in full-time education, but only in combination with computer technology, they become of a different quality and have a "second life".

Thus, the lecture material can be listened to not only in the auditorium, but also in any other place if the appropriate devices and digital communication channels are available. At the same time, the usual presentation of the training course is replaced by an electronic system of presenting the material, within which the main content of the text can be supplemented with notes and articles on the given topic. In addition, there are other forms of distance communication that are becoming more and more popular in our time: polemics, intellectual and role-playing games, joint design, creativity, conversations in forums of educational institutions.

The great development of computer technology has led to a significant transition of the "teacher-student" division to the latter. Anyone looking to fill gaps in their education or add to their personal knowledge base is virtually limitless in their choice of courses and programs currently available in the information field. He is free to find the form and method of study that is comfortable and convenient for him, to plan his time and take into account opportunities. The role of the teacher, in this case, is to guide the student in the right direction of information and to diagnose the problems that arise in mastering the material.

However, no matter how useful the innovation is, we must not forget about its disadvantages:

- introduction of computer technologies can be provided only with appropriate technological equipment;
- excessive automation depersonalizes the educational process, distances its participants from each other, the use of computer technologies leads to a reduction in social interaction and communication;
- the educational process based on computer technologies does not teach to express one's thoughts independently out loud, it focuses the student's attention on the electronic ticket;

- psychological addiction to computer work develops.

As a result of using modern search and navigation systems, certain difficulties and disadvantages appear. It is primarily about freedom, which is not easy to manage. The non-linear architecture of the found information forces the student to follow the suggested links, which can distract from the main direction of the presentation of the educational material. Another reason is the excess information, the so-called "information junk", that accompanies almost any request on the Internet. The use of computer technologies in the educational process limits live communication between the participants of the educational process. Students who are active in speech are silent for a long time when working with computer equipment, which is especially typical for distance learning. During the entire period of study, the student is mainly engaged in silent consumption of information.

The student does not have enough practice in dialogic communication, formation and formation of thoughts in professional language. Without a developed practice of dialogic communication, monologic communication with oneself, which is called independent thinking, cannot be formed. After all, the question asked to oneself is the clearest indicator of the presence of independent thinking. If we go down the path of universal individualization of education with the help of personal computers, we may miss the opportunity to develop creative thinking based on its origins in communication.

And finally, we should not forget that excessive use of computer technology has a negative effect on human health.

The following conclusions can be drawn from all of the above:

- computer technology tools have a number of advantages over traditional teaching tools;

- educational process cannot be built only on the basis of information and communication technologies.
- computer technologies require a good material and technical base and timely updating of equipment;
- the use of information and communication technologies can have negative consequences.

So, what are the consequences of using computer technologies in the educational process? Opinions will be very conflicting. Given the negative consequences of the use of computer technology listed above, someone will firmly answer "against" and, perhaps, in their way, they will be right. However, you should not overdo it: be too conservative in this matter or, on the contrary, radical. We must not forget that the man of the 21 st century lives in the era of high technologies, an incredible amount of information and ways of obtaining it. There are two sides to the question of "for" or "against" the use of computer technology.

One thing is clear: at the current stage of society's development, in the era of global information, it is impossible to ignore computer technologies and deliberately reduce their importance in the educational system. The main thing to remember is that computer technology is not a panacea, but a good teaching tool in the hands of a qualified teacher. After all, only the skill of the teacher finds the middle point in the use of computer technologies in the lesson, so that the advantages do not turn into disadvantages.

LITERATURE

1. Информационные и коммуникационные технологии в дистанционном обучении: Специальный учебный курс / пер. с англ. Майкл Г.Мур, У.Макинтош, Л.Блэк и др. М.: Издат.дом «Обучение-Сервис», 2016.
2. Бендова, Л.В. Педагогическая деятельность тьютора в сети открытого дистанционного образования: автореф. дис. канд.пед.наук. М., 2016.

3. Khonimkulov Ulugbek Suyunbaevich. (2022). THE USE OF CASE-STUDY TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF COMPUTER HARDWARE. *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 8(03), 78–81. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YT3KZ>
4. Khonimkulov Ulugbek Suyunbayevich. The use of case-study technology in the formation of students' knowledge of computer hardware//*JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*.2022 Y. 8(03), 78–81.
5. Каххоров С.К.1 , Расулова З.Д. КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ КАК ВАЖНЫЙ ФАКТОР ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕССА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ. *Современные инновации* № 2(36) 2020
6. *Rasulova Z.D.* Pedagogical peculiarities of developing socio-perceptive competence in learners. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*. Vol. 8. № 1, 2020. Pp. 30-34.